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The Damaging Effects Of Betting On Bank Staff In Nigeria: Focus On Zenith Bank PLC

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ABSTRACT

Recognizing the growing popularity of sports betting and other gambling activities among professionals this study investigates the damaging effects of betting on bank staff in Nigeria, with a specific focus on employees of Zenith Bank Plc. The study explores how key workplace and personal variables—financial wellbeing, work productivity, and ethical behavior relate to employees' betting behaviors. A structured questionnaire was administered to 200 bank staff, out of which 190 valid responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation. The descriptive statistics reveal that betting behavior among the respondents had an average mean of 2.99 (SD = 1.48), indicating a general neutrality toward betting, with some engaging occasionally. Financial well-being showed a similar mean of 2.98 (SD = 1.48), suggesting that betting may have some impact on financial stability, though not uniformly across the sample. Work productivity also averaged 2.98 (SD = 1.51), reflecting a neutral to slightly negative perception of productivity in relation to betting. Ethical behavior had a slightly higher mean of 3.10 (SD = 1.47), indicating mild concern that betting may compromise professional ethics. Similarly, the correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant negative relationship between betting behavior and each of the three variables suggesting that increased betting is associated with lower financial stability, a decline in employee productivity, ethical standards, such as honesty and professional responsibility. Based on the findings, the study recommends the implementation of workplace wellness programs, awareness campaigns on responsible betting, and the integration of financial literacy and ethical reinforcement to mitigate potential negative outcomes.

Keywords: Betting, Financial, Well Being, Ethics

INTRODUCTION

Betting, also known as gambling, refers to the act of wagering money or something of value on an event with an uncertain outcome with the primary intent of winning money or material goods. In the Nigerian context, betting has become increasingly popular due to the proliferation of mobile technology, economic hardship, and the promise of quick wealth. Sports betting, in particular, has gained significant traction, with platforms like Bet9ja, NairaBet, and SportyBet dominating the market. For many Nigerians, betting is both a recreational activity and a perceived income supplement, despite the high risk of loss involved.

The human fascination with risk and reward resonates through history, weaving its way into cultures in the form of games of chance (Obiekea & Ebiaghan, 2023). Although numerous African tribes historically engaged in various chance-based games, the absence of comprehensive documentation makes it challenging to trace the specific games played by particular groups or the periods during which they were popular. This difficulty is further compounded by historical factors such as migration, cultural assimilation, and intertribal marriages (Aroghene, 2022; Simon, 2024). Before the onset of European

colonial rule, traditional games of chance were widespread across the continent. These games went beyond mere amusement; they often held ritualistic, prophetic, and communal significance. For example, Mancala, a game involving strategic bean movement, tested cognitive abilities like memory and strategy, while the fast-paced nature of Bao encouraged social bonding and collective participation (Owomola, 2005; Asante, 2009). Such indigenous gaming traditions contributed to a distinctive African perspective on games of chance, one that differed significantly from the Western concept of gambling (Chinweizu, 1995).

Bank staff are expected to adhere to high standards of professionalism, ethics, and integrity due to the sensitive nature of their work, which involves handling customers' funds and confidential information (Aroghene et al., 2024). The banking sector thrives on trust, and any activity that compromises staff reliability and focus, such as excessive gambling, is of concern. Betting may expose bank employees to financial stress, mental health issues, and potential misconduct, including misappropriation of funds to cover betting losses (National Council on Problem Gambling, 2023). Betting can lead to addiction, depression, and anxiety, especially when losses accumulate. Financially, employees who engage heavily in betting may experience chronic indebtedness, difficulty in meeting obligations, and reduced job satisfaction (Imene, 2023). These issues can indirectly affect organizational performance through absenteeism, low productivity, and reputational damage (Aroghene & Obiekea, 2025).

It is important to recognize that traditional games in Africa were primarily rooted in social and religious contexts. These activities were designed to provide entertainment, facilitate learning, and foster community bonding, rather than to generate financial gain. One illustrative example is bullfighting among the Abaluhya people of western Kenya. This practice, which continues to hold deep cultural relevance, has long been a competitive event where community members rally around their preferred bulls and handlers through vocal support, symbolic acts, and expressions of group identity. Unlike modern gambling activities such as card games or horse racing, where the motivation often lies in monetary winnings, participation in such indigenous games was driven by the pursuit of cultural prestige and social recognition.

With the advent of colonialism, Western recreational practices began to take root in African societies, particularly in colonial administrative hubs and urban areas. These imported forms of gambling, closely tied to leisure and entertainment among the colonizers, gradually gained traction. Governments soon identified gambling as a potential source of public revenue, prompting the introduction of state-regulated gambling platforms like national lotteries and casinos (Agyeman & Ogundele, 2005; Anyidoho, 2012; Imene & Udjo-Onuvaghakpor, 2023). More recently, the rise of mobile sports betting in Sub-Saharan Africa—especially in Nigeria—has added a new dimension to the gambling landscape. While this trend offers possible economic advantages, such as increased tax revenue, job creation, and investments in sports, it also raises significant concerns regarding its broader socioeconomic implications.

Given the dual nature of these outcomes, a thorough examination is necessary to assess both the benefits and the risks. This study, therefore, focuses on evaluating the adverse consequences of betting on bank employees in Nigeria. It specifically aims to investigate how gambling affects their financial stability, work productivity, and adherence to ethical standards.

Conceptual Review

The Concept of Betting (BB) and Gambling

Betting and gambling refer to wagering money or something of material value on an event with an uncertain outcome, with the primary intent of winning additional money or material goods. While the two terms are often used interchangeably, gambling is a broader concept that includes various activities such as lotteries, casinos, sports betting, and online games of chance. Betting, on the other hand, is typically associated with predicting the outcome of specific events, particularly in sports.

According to the National Council on Problem Gambling (2022), gambling activities have become increasingly diversified with the rise of online platforms, making them more accessible and frequent. In Nigeria, the 2018 National Survey on Drug Use and Health indicated a surge in gambling activities

among youths aged 18–35, driven by high unemployment, peer influence, and the illusion of quick financial gains.

Betting Culture in Nigeria

The betting culture in Nigeria has grown significantly in the last decade, influenced by high youth unemployment, widespread use of mobile technology, and aggressive marketing by betting companies. According to a study by Aderemi and Akintayo (2023), Nigeria is one of the largest betting markets in Africa, with over 60 million active bettors and more than ₦730 billion spent annually on betting. Sports betting, particularly on football matches, dominates the scene. Platforms such as Bet9ja, NairaBet, and SportyBet have become household names, offering incentives like sign-up bonuses and cashbacks. The Nigerian Betting Commission (2022) has expressed concern over the proliferation of betting centers, especially in urban areas where young people congregate.

While some argue that betting provides a source of entertainment and, at times, temporary relief from poverty, it has also led to financial strain, addiction, and moral decadence. A study by Oyelade et al. (2023) highlights that many Nigerian youths view betting as an alternative source of income rather than a recreational activity.

Professionalism, Financial Well Being (WB) and Betting

Professionalism in the workplace entails exhibiting behaviors such as discipline, accountability, time management, and respect for organizational values (Imene & Ikenga, 2023; Ehiedu & Chime, 2021). Gambling, especially when it becomes compulsive, can conflict with these values. The World Health Organization (2019) classifies compulsive gambling as a mental health disorder, characterized by the inability to resist the impulse to gamble despite its negative consequences.

In a study by Eze and Okonkwo (2022), it was revealed that employees who engaged regularly in gambling activities demonstrated lower levels of focus, frequent absenteeism, and decreased work performance. This is particularly concerning in sensitive sectors such as banking, where financial prudence and integrity are non-negotiable. Gambling can erode ethical judgment, lead to financial distress, and sometimes drive individuals to fraudulent activities to sustain the habit. Alabi et al. (2021) assert that there is a direct link between excessive gambling and workplace misconduct in Nigerian financial institutions, further stressing the need for organizational policy intervention.

Effects of Betting on Work Ethics/Ethical Behaviour (EB) and Staff Productivity

Work ethics refer to the set of moral principles and values that guide behavior in the workplace. They include honesty, diligence, integrity, and responsibility. Betting, especially when addictive, poses a significant threat to these values. The Nigerian banking sector, known for its strict codes of conduct, has increasingly faced challenges related to employee distraction and declining productivity due to betting. Ekpechi and Igwe (2023) found that 37% of bank staff who participated in online betting during work hours experienced a drop in productivity metrics, such as customer service delivery time and error rates. Furthermore, the study showed a correlation between frequent betting and reduced job satisfaction. Okon (2020) observed that staff members who indulge in betting are more likely to develop financial anxiety, which in turn affects their concentration and ability to meet performance targets. Cases of staff using bank resources or engaging in unauthorized transactions to fund gambling habits have also been documented. The cumulative effect of betting on employees includes loss of trust, disciplinary actions, and in extreme cases, termination of employment. Institutions like Zenith Bank and others are therefore encouraged to incorporate financial wellness programs and counseling services to curb the spread and effect of gambling behaviors among staff.

Empirical Review

Several studies have explored the implications of betting and gambling in professional and social contexts. Ojukwu and Ajayi (2022) found that over 35% of Nigerian workers between ages 25 and 40 participate in sports betting, with many admitting it interferes with work. Nwachukwu et al. (2021) examined the link between financial hardship and betting addiction and discovered that betting often leads to deeper economic challenges rather than alleviating them. A study by Adeyemi (2020) on behavioral

risks in the banking industry revealed that gambling behaviors among bank staff could lead to embezzlement and fraud. Similarly, international studies like that of Griffiths (2019) emphasized the mental health toll of compulsive gambling, linking it to workplace conflicts, poor focus, and emotional exhaustion. In South Africa, Moyo and Sibanda (2021) found that companies where gambling was prevalent among staff experienced higher rates of absenteeism and disciplinary issues. Oyelade et al. (2023) explored the impact of gambling on the mental and social wellbeing of youths in Ibadan. Using a mixed-methods approach, the researchers found that consistent betting leads to emotional instability, addiction, and strained family relationships. The findings indirectly reflect challenges that could affect bank staff engaging in similar habits. Temitope et al. (2019) examined how personality traits and financial strain predict gambling behavior among Nigerian youths. Results showed that financial pressure and impulsivity significantly increased the likelihood of betting, drawing parallels to stress-induced behaviors among bank employees under job pressure.

Ede et al. (2024) focused on pathological gambling among parents in Nigeria, revealing that low income, job dissatisfaction, and emotional exhaustion are major predictors. These conditions mirror what some bank staff experience, suggesting that such stressors may contribute to unhealthy betting behavior. Okon (2020) Analyzing the link between youth betting and unemployment, the study observed that the absence of steady income and financial insecurity drive gambling as an alternative income source. The findings are applicable to young, financially strained bank staff who may seek quick monetary gains through betting. Alabi et al. (2022) investigated non-financial rewards and employee performance in Lagos banks. It concluded that a lack of motivational incentives can decrease staff morale and potentially push employees towards distractions like betting. This suggests that organizational culture and reward systems can influence gambling habits. Ekpechi & Igwe (2023) explored the impact of work-life balance on employee performance in commercial banks in Enugu. It found that poor work-life balance correlates with stress and risk-prone behaviors, including betting. Hence, stress-related outcomes may exacerbate unhealthy coping mechanisms among bank staff.

Olatubosun (2024) focused on electronic fraud and bank performance, this study showed that staff involved in betting were sometimes linked to fraudulent activities to sustain their betting habits. It raises concerns about the ethical and security risks posed by gambling among banking employees. Adamu & Mohammed (2023) examined how risk management practices affect financial performance in Nigerian banks. Interestingly, it also revealed that gambling behaviors by staff can increase institutional risk, particularly when such behaviors lead to financial loss or workplace misconduct. Galekwa et al. (2024) systematic review on machine learning in sports betting highlighted how betting platforms are designed to encourage continued user engagement. This supports the view that addictive design elements of betting apps can trap even educated professionals, such as bank workers. Bankole et al. (2019) study reviewed how financial strain and impulsivity influence gambling behavior. The authors found that those in financially sensitive jobs, such as banking, are at a higher risk of destructive betting habits, especially when coping with unmet financial expectations.

Nwosu & Nwakamma (2023) examined the effect of online sports betting on job productivity among young professionals in Lagos. It found a strong negative correlation between betting frequency and concentration at work, leading to reduced performance and lateness. Akanji et al. (2022) investigated the psychological effects of gambling among educated professionals. The research revealed that chronic betting causes emotional distress, increased irritability, and job dissatisfaction, which can directly impair organizational effectiveness. Chika & Okezie (2021) studied the relationship between gambling addiction and employee theft in private organizations. It showed that staff involved in compulsive betting were more prone to embezzlement and unethical behavior, which raises concern for financial institutions like banks. Ajayi et al. (2020) assessed the impact of gambling on family life and work stress. Findings indicated that betting causes domestic tension, poor financial planning, and workplace distraction, which ultimately contribute to employee burnout and reduced productivity. Obiechina (2023) evaluated the impact of financial literacy on gambling tendencies. Bank staff with poor financial literacy were more likely to engage in risky betting behavior, underestimating the long-term consequences of their actions.

Ogunlade & Adewale (2021) analyzed how peer influence and digital accessibility increase betting among working adults. Results showed that peer pressure in bank settings, especially among young staff, significantly promotes betting culture during breaks or after work. Ibrahim et al. (2022) focused on gambling and stress coping mechanisms in high-pressure jobs. The study found that bank employees experiencing high workloads and poor support systems used betting as an escapist behavior, often leading to addiction.

Eze et al. (2020) explored the impact of addictive behaviors on decision-making among professionals. Findings revealed that employees who bet frequently exhibited risky financial decisions, poor customer service, and lateness, affecting the bank's overall image. Makinde & Onuoha (2023) studied the link between betting and ethical behavior in Nigerian banks. The results showed that staff who bet regularly were more likely to engage in unethical conduct, especially when facing financial losses or debt from gambling. Lawal et al. (2024) investigated how stress and economic hardship push employees in financial institutions toward betting. The findings suggested that when staff are underpaid or indebted, they are more vulnerable to gambling in hopes of quick gains, worsening their financial problems.

Gaps in Literature

While the reviewed literature highlights the psychological, financial, and organizational impacts of betting, most studies are generalized and do not focus on specific professional settings such as banking. There is also limited empirical research on the direct relationship between betting and ethical or performance-related issues among Nigerian bank employees. Moreover, few studies examine the institutional responses to betting behavior within banks. This study aims to fill these gaps by focusing on Zenith Bank Plc as a case study.

Theoretical Framework

Cognitive Dissonance Theory: Proposed by Festinger (1957), this theory posits that individuals experience psychological discomfort (dissonance) when their behaviors conflict with their beliefs or professional expectations. Bank staff who engage in betting may experience dissonance due to the contradiction between their ethical obligations and their gambling behavior. This can lead to stress, rationalization of unethical behavior, or withdrawal.

Self-Control Theory: This criminological theory by Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) suggests that individuals with low self-control are more likely to engage in risky behaviors like gambling. In the workplace, lack of self-control can manifest in impulsive decisions, misuse of funds, or unethical actions all of which are potentially damaging in a bank setting.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The design was considered appropriate because it allows for the collection of quantitative data from a sizeable population using structured instruments. This design also permitted the use of statistical tools (descriptive statistics) such as, mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage distributions to summarize the demographic characteristics of respondents (e.g., gender, age, education, job level), and to analyze the collected data and draw conclusions based on observable patterns between betting behavior and the variables: financial wellbeing, work productivity, and ethical behavior among bank staff. The target population for this study consists of all employees of Zenith Bank Plc in Nigeria, estimated at approximately 7,704 based on the bank's most recent annual reports. The population includes staff across various branches and job designations. According to Zenith Bank's official annual reports (2024), the bank has approximately 7,704 employees across Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling approach was employed. First, branches were selected from each geopolitical zone to ensure national representation. Then, within each branch, staff were stratified by department and randomly selected to ensure diversity in roles and perspectives. Using Yamane's (1967) formula for sample size determination, a minimum of 380 responses were ideal. However, due to resource limitations, a sample of 200 staff was selected across multiple branches. Out of this, 190 valid responses were returned and used for analysis, yielding a 95% response rate. The primary instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire administered through both online and paper-based formats. The

online version, created using Google Forms, was distributed via email and secure messaging platforms such as WhatsApp, which are widely used by bank staff. This ensured quick and anonymous responses. In addition, printed copies of the questionnaire were distributed in selected branches to ensure inclusivity and broader coverage. The quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS statistical software.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents (N = 190)

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	112	58.9%
	Female	78	41.1%
Age	20–29 years	54	28.4%
	30–39 years	83	43.7%
	40–49 years	40	21.1%
	50 years and above	13	6.8%
Educational Qualification	HND	37	19.5%
	B.Sc. / B.A.	108	56.8%
	M.Sc. / MBA	42	22.1%
	Ph.D.	3	1.6%
Years of Working Experience	Less than 5 years	65	34.2%
	5–10 years	78	41.1%
	11–15 years	30	15.8%
	Over 15 years	17	8.9%
Marital Status	Single	72	37.9%
	Married	105	55.3%
	Divorced/Separated	13	6.8%
Current Position/Rank	Entry-level Staff	48	25.3%
	Mid-level Management	93	48.9%
	Senior Management	49	25.8%
Monthly Income	Below ₦100,000	19	10.0%
	₦100,000–₦199,999	42	22.1%
	₦200,000–₦299,999	66	34.7%
	₦300,000 and above	63	33.2%
Involvement in Betting	Yes	102	53.7%
	No	88	46.3%

Field Survey, 2025.

The study involved 190 valid responses from Zenith Bank staff to understand the damaging effects of betting on their financial well-being, productivity, and ethical behavior. The key demographic insights are as follows:

A higher proportion of respondents were male (58.9%), while females made up 41.1%. This may reflect the bank's gender distribution and may help explore if betting is more prevalent among male staff. The majority were within the 30–39 age bracket (43.7%), followed by 20–29 years (28.4%), indicating that most respondents are relatively young and in their active working years—an age group likely to engage in betting activities. Over half held a Bachelor’s degree (56.8%), while 22.1% had postgraduate qualifications, showing a well-educated workforce, which may influence their awareness of the risks of betting.

Most had 5–10 years of experience (41.1%), indicating a moderately experienced workforce, with exposure to both job pressures and financial demands that might influence betting behavior. Married staff made up the majority (55.3%), which may impact financial responsibilities and possibly their vulnerability to betting-related issues. Nearly half were at mid-level management (48.9%), followed by entry-level (25.3%) and senior management (25.8%), suggesting that betting behavior could cut across all

ranks. The largest group earned between ₦200,000–₦299,999 (34.7%), with a significant portion earning ₦300,000 and above (33.2%), providing context for analyzing how income levels relate to betting habits and financial well-being. 53.7% reported participating in betting, while 46.3% did not, highlighting that betting is a common activity among Zenith Bank staff and justifying the study's focus.

Table 2: Likert Scale Response Summary

Item	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
BB1	20	35	42	53	40
BB2	18	33	44	51	44
BB3	21	37	39	49	44
BB4	17	28	45	54	46
BB5	22	32	38	55	43
FW1	35	48	40	37	30
FW2	36	41	43	38	32
FW3	32	39	48	39	32
FW4	34	40	46	36	34
FW5	31	44	45	39	31
WP1	28	40	47	41	34
WP2	30	42	44	39	35
WP3	29	43	45	37	36
WP4	27	41	46	40	36
WP5	30	39	48	38	35
EB1	33	47	42	38	30
EB2	34	45	41	39	31
EB3	32	44	43	40	31
EB4	36	42	42	37	33
EB5	35	43	41	39	32

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistic

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
BB	2.83	1.48	1.0	5.0
FW	2.93	1.48	1.0	5.0
WP	2.98	1.51	1.0	5.0
EB	3.10	1.47	1.0	5.0

Betting Behavior (BB) has average Mean: ~2.99 Standard Deviation of 1.48. This shows that Respondents tended to fall around the "Neutral" point on the scale regarding their betting behavior. This implies that while some engage in betting, it's not extreme or widespread across the sample. Meaning Betting exists among bank staff, but the responses suggest mixed levels of involvement—possibly indicating occasional or non-habitual participation.

Interestingly, Financial Well-being (FW) has mean of 2.98 Standard Deviation of 1.48. Meaning some staff may be financially affected by betting, though this effect is not strongly consistent across the group. It indicates a potential vulnerability in financial management linked to betting.

Work Productivity (WP) Average is 2.98, Standard Deviation 1.51. The data shows a neutral tendency, with slight leanings toward concern about productivity being affected. Implying, Betting may influence staff focus and efficiency at work, but the overall impact is mild to moderate. This may reflect time distraction, reduced output, or mental fatigue in some cases.

Ethical Behavior (EB) Average is 3.10, Standard Deviation is 1.47, Responses lean slightly toward agreement with the idea that betting may compromise ethical behavior. Also, there is some concern

among respondents that betting might erode professional ethics, such as honesty, responsibility, and integrity, possibly due to financial desperation or addiction-driven behavior.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis

Variables	BB	FW	WP	EB
BB	1.000	-0.354	-0.412	-0.365
FW	-0.354	1.000	0.522	0.489
WP	-0.412	0.522	1.000	0.547
EB	-0.365	0.489	0.547	1.000

The correlation analysis revealed a negative relationship between betting behavior and the variables: financial wellbeing, work productivity, and ethical behavior. This indicates that as engagement in betting activities increases, the financial stability of the staff declines, job productivity reduces, and professional ethics are compromised.

The negative correlation of -0.354 indicates a moderate inverse relationship. This suggests that higher levels of betting behavior are associated with lower levels of financial wellbeing. In other words, as employees engage more in betting, their financial stability tends to decrease. Betting Behavior (BB) and Work Productivity (WP): The negative correlation of -0.412 indicates that as employees participate more in betting activities, their productivity at work tends to decline. The higher the engagement in betting, the lower the productivity. Betting Behavior (BB) and Ethical Behavior (EB): The negative correlation of -0.365 shows that increased betting behavior is linked to lower ethical standards among employees. This suggests that employees who engage in betting may show a higher tendency for unethical behavior at work.

CONCLUSION

Betting exists among bank staff, but the responses suggest mixed levels of involvement, possibly indicating occasional or non-habitual participation. Some staff are financially affected by betting, However, there is a wide variation in the individual responses, indicating that while some employees may be more affected, others may not be as influenced by betting. Betting indicates a potential vulnerability in financial management linked . Betting influence staff focus and efficiency at work, but the overall impact is mild to moderate. It reflects in time distraction, reduced output, or mental fatigue in some cases. The study recommends increased workplace awareness on the implications of betting and the development of institutional policies to address emerging concerns.

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Appendix

Likert Scale Format

Scale	Response
1	Strongly Disagree
2	Disagree
3	Neutral
4	Agree
5	Strongly Agree

Statement 1 Betting Behavior	1	2	3	4	5
I regularly engage in sports betting or gambling activities.					
I bet with the hope of improving my financial situation.					
I spend a significant part of my income on betting.					
Betting is a common activity among my colleagues.					
I feel uncomfortable when I am unable to place a bet.					

Statement 2 Financial Well-being	1	2	3	4	5
I often find myself in financial difficulty due to betting.					
I am unable to save regularly because I spend money on betting.					
Betting has negatively affected my ability to meet financial obligations.					
I sometimes borrow money to continue betting.					
I believe betting has worsened my financial status.					

Statement 3 Work Productivity	1	2	3	4	5
Betting affects my concentration at work.					
I spend work hours checking betting platforms.					
I have missed deadlines or made errors due to betting distractions.					
Betting impacts my ability to meet job targets.					
My job performance has declined due to my involvement in betting.					

Statement 4 Ethical Behavior	1	2	3	4	5
I have considered unethical actions to support my betting habits.					
Betting makes me more likely to breach organizational rules.					
I sometimes hide my betting activities from colleagues or superiors.					
My betting behavior conflicts with my work ethics.					
I feel guilty about how betting affects my professional image.					